

WorldCOM deliverable D-JRP13-2.1: Multiplex real-time isothermal assays for pathogens and antimicrobial resistance genes, which will be suitable for use in laboratory and optimised further in WP3 into a format suitable for on-site use

Antimicrobial resistance (AMR) is a global problem affecting both human and animal health. The over-use and miss-use of antibiotics is the main driver of AMR, and therefore better diagnostics and interventions are urgently required. The rapid detection of AMR targets is crucial for identifying appropriate treatments, monitoring outbreaks and preventing the further spread of AMR. Loop-mediated isothermal amplification (LAMP) is a rapid diagnostic platform for the detection of nucleic acid targets without the need for a thermocycler and thus facilitating bed-side and pen-side testing.

In this project, multiplex LAMP assays were developed to rapidly detect AMR biomarkers. LAMP primers were designed to specifically target plasmid-mediated colistin resistance (*mcr-1*), KPC-mediated carbapenem resistance (KPC), oxacillin-hydrolysing β -lactamases (OXA-48 and OXA-23 genes) and Verona Integron-encoded Metallo- β -lactamase (VIM). The developed assays were optimised to detect the targeted conserved sequences rapidly and sensitively from different water and faecal samples rapidly and sensitively. The assays can be implemented as bed-side and/or pen-side diagnostics to facilitate the rapid detection of AMR.

Next to the AMR biomarkers described above, cefotaximases (CTX-Ms) have been targeted for diagnostic assays. Cefotaximases (CTX-Ms) are extended-spectrum beta-lactamase (ESBL) enzymes found in Enterobacteriaceae such as *Escherichia coli* that confer resistance to third-generation cephalosporin antibiotics. Dissemination of CTX-M group 1 variants *bla*_{CTX-M-1} and *bla*_{CTX-M-15}, typically associated with animal and human infection, respectively, is a public-health concern that requires effective diagnostics. However, *bla*_{CTX-M-1} and *bla*_{CTX-M-15} variants are almost identical in sequence and difficult to differentiate using conventional molecular diagnostics.

Loop-primer Endonuclease Cleavage loop-mediated isothermal amplification (LEC-LAMP) enables rapid real-time multiplex pathogen detection with single-base specificity and portable on-site testing. We have developed an internally controlled multiplex LEC-LAMP assay for the differential detection of antimicrobial resistance markers *bla*_{CTX-M-1} and *bla*_{CTX-M-15} in a single reaction. This technology was evaluated in combination with a rapid DNA extraction protocol using culture-confirmed CTX-M-1 positive porcine faecal samples. The internally controlled CTX-M-1/15 LEC-LAMP assay demonstrated specific and sensitive differential detection of the *bla*_{CTX-M-1} and *bla*_{CTX-M-15} variants, and successfully detected CTX-M-1 from porcine faecal samples in combination with a rapid DNA extraction method. This is the first report of such nucleic acid diagnostics technology with the potential for portable on-site testing, that can provide effective differential detection of *bla*_{CTX-M-1} and *bla*_{CTX-M-15}.